

AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO DESIGN AND MONITOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES UNDER IN-SERVICE FATIGUE LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue failure and in-service loss of stiffness of composite parts are due to a multi-mechanism damage evolution which mainly includes cracks, delamination and fibre failures. This work presents an innovative, comprehensive framework for the fatigue design of composite parts, based on the actual physics of damage evolution. The initiation and growth of each mechanism, its interaction with the others and the effects on the strength and stiffness of the parts are described by suitable models and experimentally validated. The combination of all these models into a single design framework provides a highly innovative design tool as well as an enormous increase in the safety and reliability of the structural applications in composites. The in-service reliability and safety of these parts can be further improved by using a new structural health monitoring methodology. This methodology, based on the exploitation of the self-sensing capabilities of conductive nano-modified laminates, allows the continuous assessment of the damage state and the correlation of its evolution with the residual elastic properties of the composite parts. Damage induced by unexpected events can be also monitored.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced polymeric composites for structural applications has been tremendously growing in the last years due to the thrust of dominating industrial fields like aerospace, automotive and wind energy. In this context of significant growth, it is rather easy to understand the safety and long-term reliability requirements of a composite part, when thinking for instance to a design life of 25 year as for a turbine blade or more than 200,000 km as for a high performance car frame. At the same time, the high level of performance have to be frequently associated with a stringent cost-effective design for costs reasons and product sustainability. In few words, future high performance composite structures have to be reliable, safe and cost-effective.

Turning now on the other side of the coin, high performance structures are frequently subjected to severe working conditions, undergoing complex multiaxial cyclic loads, which may induce stiffness loss due to damage and eventually failure. The long-term (fatigue) performance is therefore critical for the design.

It is also important to mention that, given the complex behaviour of composite materials under cyclic loading, characterised by multiple interacting damage mechanisms, the design against fatigue can be meant in different ways according to the field of application and design requirements:

- i) Design against crack initiation (the initiation of any crack must be avoided);
- ii) Design against stiffness loss (a certain damage can be tolerated when it does not lead to a stiffness degradation higher than a certain threshold);
- iii) Design against failure (the complete failure, i.e. complete loss of load bearing capability, must be avoided).

In the authors' opinion, the only way to deal with such a complicated problem and provide efficient and reliable design methods is to develop models based on the damage mechanisms actually occurring at the several length scales and link them in a multiscale and multi-mechanism design procedure. This would be extremely useful for increasing the reliability of composite structures, but also decreasing their cost. Indeed, the possibility to carry out virtual experiments would allow to design optimized solutions and to decrease the need of expensive and time-consuming experimental tests.

As mentioned, structural applications may lead to the presence of damage in the material. In addition, composite parts may be subjected to unexpected events such as impacts, causing a localized damage in the form of cracks and delamination. In most of the cases, the internal damage may be barely detectable by visual inspection. Therefore, tools for the health monitoring of composite structures are highly desirable in many applications to increase their safety and reliability. Among the several techniques available for this purpose, electrical methods received a particular attention in the last decade in virtue of their easiness of applicability (no sensors are needed) and the possibility to carry out a continuous and real-time monitoring.

In the last decade, the Composite Materials Group at the University of Padova has intensively worked on the two research lines highlighted above (damage prediction and electrical health monitoring), finding an enormous potential in the combination of predictive models and health monitoring for increasing the reliability, safety and cost-effectiveness of composite parts.

In this paper, after an outline of the damage mechanisms observed during the fatigue life of composite laminates, the models developed for predicting the damage evolution, the stiffness loss and their correlation with the electrical properties (for the sake of health monitoring) will be briefly presented.

2 EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCES OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION

The damage evolution in composite materials is a multiscale and hierarchical process, involving several mechanisms at different length scales. In this work, the macro-scale is related to the ply and laminate level, whereas the micro-scale is relevant to the fibres and the inter-fibre spacing.

As widely proved in the literature (see Refs. [1-6] among the others), the first macro-scale damage event in a multidirectional laminate is represented by the initiation of off-axis cracks that typically involve the entire thickness of a ply and propagate along the fibre direction. The crack density increases during the lifetime and a saturation condition is reached after a certain number of cycles. A second important mechanism is represented by delamination. A delamination initiates from the tips of the off-axis cracks at the interface with confining layers and propagates in a direction normal to the off-axis cracks. These two mechanisms are not directly responsible for the laminate failure but cause a significant loss of the apparent stiffness that must be correctly predicted if a damage tolerant design approach is adopted. An example of the damage evolution, highlighting the multiplication of off-axis cracks, is shown in Figure 1.

The final failure is then typically controlled by the main load bearing plies, which means that it is caused by the failure of the 0° -oriented fibres.

Figure 1: Example of fatigue damage evolution and failure in a $[0/60_2/0/-60_2]_s$ laminate [6]

In a damage-based approach, criteria for predicting the onset and evolution of the macroscopic damage modes highlighted above should be based on the damage evolution at the lower scale, i.e. the micro-scale.

With the aim of identifying the microscopic damage mechanisms leading to the initiation of an off-axis crack, glass/epoxy $[45/-45/0]_s$ laminates were tested by the authors under a uniaxial cyclic load [7]. At regular intervals the specimens were removed from the machine and their top surface,

previously polished, was observed under a microscope. The first event of damage at the micro-scale, before the initiation of a visible off-axis crack, was the initiation of micro-cracks in the matrix, inclined with respect to the fibre direction (Figure 2). The accumulation and coalescence of these micro-cracks led then to the initiation of an off-axis crack propagating in the fibre direction. It was shown that also the propagation phenomenon occurred with a similar mechanism, i.e. by the initiation and coalescence of micro-cracks in a region in front of the macro-crack tip [7]. This mechanism is typical of local stress states characterized by a significant shear stress level (with a biaxiality ratio $\lambda_{12}=\sigma_6/\sigma_2$ typically higher than 0.5).

Figure 2: Micrograph of a 45° ply in a [45/-45/0]_s laminate under a cyclic load [7]

After identifying the micro-scale damage modes leading to the initiation and propagation of an off-axis crack, the delamination and fibre failure phenomena were analysed from the microscopic point of view. Fatigue tests were carried out on glass/epoxy cross-ply laminates. Again, multiple transverse cracks were seen to initiate and propagate. The crack density saturation was slightly preceded by the initiation of delaminations. Edge micrographs of the specimens were taken, revealing a typical scenario as shown in Figure 3. As expected, the delaminations were triggered by the presence of the transverse cracks and then propagated at the interface.

The role that transverse cracks and delamination play on the failure of the fibres is clear from Figure 3. In fact, 0° fibre breaks are concentrated in the vicinity of the transverse crack tip and above the delamination, of which the evolution brings to more and more fibre breaks, until a critical condition is reached.

Figure 3: Example of delamination from a transverse crack tip with broken fibres

3 MODELLING DAMAGE EVOLUTION AND STIFFNESS LOSS

According to the experimental observations at the macro- and micro-scales, the fatigue life of a composite laminate has to be divided in different phases, each characterized by a dominating damage mode. Therefore, for predicting the fatigue behaviour of a composite laminate, the initiation and evolution of each mechanism has to be predicted, together with its effect on the stress re-distribution and the stiffness degradation. In particular, for a safe and efficient design against fatigue it is necessary to:

- i) Predict the cycles spent for crack initiation;
- ii) Describe the crack propagation and the crack density evolution until the saturation condition;
- iii) Predicting the cycles spent for the delamination initiation and propagation;
- iv) Predicting the cycles spent for the failure of the fibres and the final laminate failure.

For each mechanism, the associated stiffness reduction must be predicted as well.

According to this strategy, a procedure for predicting the damage evolution in composite laminates has been developed by the authors, integrating the following predictive models and criteria:

- 1) A criterion for predicting the off-axis fatigue crack initiation under multiaxial stress states [8];
- 2) A mixed mode propagation criterion [9];
- 3) Analytical models for describing the stress re-distributions and the stiffness degradation in the presence of off-axis cracks [10] and delamination [11];
- 4) A model for predicting the crack density evolution under a generic multiaxial loading, also under variable amplitude conditions [12];
- 5) A delamination propagation tool based on a power law correlating the delamination growth rate to the Energy Release Rate (ERR) [13].

As mentioned, the criteria for the initiation and propagation of off-axis cracks, based on the damage mechanisms observed at the micro-scale, make use of local stress and energy parameters calculated through micro-scale Representative Volume Elements (RVEs). The ply-level stress distributions and the stiffness degradation are instead predicted by means of a shear lag analysis of a macro-scale RVE that includes damage in multiple plies [10-11]. Eventually, the ERR for the delamination propagation is calculated by means of FE analyses of macro-scale volume elements through the VCCT method.

The entire framework was validated by means of experimental data, revealing a very good agreement both in terms of damage evolution and stiffness loss. Representative examples are reported in Figs. 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Validation of the procedure in terms of a) crack density and b) stiffness loss for a $[0/45_2/0/-45_2]_s$ laminate [12]

Figure 5: Validation of the procedure in terms of a) crack density and delaminated area % and b) stiffness loss for a $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate

4 ELECTRICAL HEALTH MONITORING

Each of the damage mechanisms described in section 2 causes discontinuities in the material. If an electrically conductive network is available in the composite (obtained for instance by means of carbon fibres and/or CNT-modified epoxy resins), such discontinuities will break the network causing a change in the material electrical response. This results, in fact, in an increased apparent electrical resistivity, that is therefore strictly connected to the damage state. Therefore, by using electrical measurements, the presence of damage in the form of off-axis cracks, delamination and fibre failure can be detected.

To this end it was also essential to develop analytical models to correlate the electrical resistance increase to the amount of damage, analytical models were developed by the authors in the recent years.

In Particular, Zappalorto et al. [14] developed an analytical model to assess the electric potential distribution of a conductive composite plate in the presence of a delamination between the central plies. The model was validated first by comparison with finite element analyses on plates with different geometries and electrical properties, and later against the results of a dedicated combined electrical-mechanical experimental campaign carried out on DCB specimens [14]. Through this model it was possible to correlate, with a very good accuracy, the electrical resistance increase with the delamination length (see Figure 6 as an example). The model allowed also to understand the role played by the main geometrical and material parameters in the resistance change and therefore their effect on the sensitivity of the method for damage monitoring. In particular, it was found that:

1. The resistance change is higher for lower through-the-thickness to longitudinal resistivity ratios, thus documenting that decreasing the resistivity ratio, for instance by modification of the resin with CNTs or other conductive particles, can lead to a higher accuracy;
2. Thinner panels provide a higher resistance change and are therefore better candidates to be monitored by means of electrical methods;
3. The laminate lay-up has a non-negligible effect on the sensitivity of the method.

The presence of off-axis cracks can also be detected by means of resistivity measurements. In particular, considering a $[(\theta_1)_m/(\theta_2)_n]_s$ laminate made of unidirectional plies, with off-axis cracks in the θ_2 layers, Panozzo et al. [15] proposed a closed form solution for the laminate electrical resistance as a function of the crack density and the electrical properties of the plies. Using such a model in combination with the shear lag model for the cracked laminate [10], it was also possible to obtain a direct correlation between the electrical resistance increase and the elastic modulus degradation. An example is shown in Figure 7, where the analytical predictions are also compared with the results of a number of numerical analyses. It is evident that a well defined correlation exists between stiffness drop and electrical resistance increase, and such a correlation is properly described by the model given in [15]. These tools can be used for an electrically-based indirect measurement of the elastic properties of a damaged laminate.

In Ref. [15] a detailed parametrical analysis was also carried out to highlight the effect of the most influencing material and geometrical parameters, which were identified to be the orientation of the

plies (θ_1 and θ_2), the thickness of the plies (h_1 and h_2) and the ratio between the in-plane and out-of-plane conductivities. Based on the results the following main conclusions were drawn:

- the highest increase of the electrical resistance, for a given value of elastic modulus degradation, is obtained for the case of $\theta_1 = 0^\circ$, and the sensitivity decreases for higher θ_1 angles;
- for a given value of elastic modulus degradation, the electrical resistance change of laminates with low values of θ_2 is low, reaching a maximum at 55° , and slightly decreases for higher values of the off-axis angle;
- laminates with lower anisotropy ratio (i.e., higher out-of-plane conductivity) are characterized by a higher sensitivity, since the increase of the electrical resistance for a given value of the elastic modulus drop is higher;

Figure 6: Experimental results and comparison with the analytical model for a DCB specimen [14]

Figure 7: Influence of the orientation angle θ_2 on the electrical/mechanical response of the cracked laminate [15].

When conductive fibres are adopted, electrical methods can be also used for monitoring the fibre failure process, as reported in the literature [16].

5 AN INTEGRATED APPROACH

As already mentioned, the damage predictive procedure and the developed health monitoring models represent, on their own, innovative and useful tools in the design and management of composite parts. However, a proper combination of these two frameworks may lead to a tremendous increase in the reliability, safety and cost-effectiveness of composite structures.

A schematic of the integrated approach is shown in Figure 8. It can be articulated in the following steps:

- 1) Once the proper ply mechanical properties, the lay-up and loading condition are known, the damage evolution under cyclic loadings can be predicted through the proposed multi-scale and multi-mechanism procedure;
- 2) Through the optimised shear lag model the stiffness degradation can be also predicted;
- 3) Simulations can be carried out by the designer seeking for an optimised material and geometrical configuration;
- 4) Knowing the ply electrical properties and the lay-up, an electrodes placement configuration can be chosen, with the help of the developed analytical models, to maximise the sensitivity of electrical measurements (also the material properties can be tailored according to specific needs);
- 5) The resistance-stiffness correlation can be predicted by the analytical models for the material, geometry and electrodes' configuration chosen;
- 6) Electrical measurements are carried out during the in-service life, to serve as an indirect measurement of the composite part stiffness;
- 7) By comparing the stiffness prediction to these measurements, the predictive procedure can be validated in service. In addition, unexpected events, such as overloads or impacts, can be identified and their severity evaluated, thus increasing the structural safety and reliability.

Figure 8: Schematic of the integrated approach

6 CONCLUSIONS

A damage-based multi-scale and multi-mechanism framework was developed by the authors to predict the damage evolution and the associated stiffness loss in composite laminates under cyclic loads. At the same time, models were developed to correlate the damage state and the stiffness degradation to the electrical properties of damaged laminates, to serve as a tool for the continuous and real-time health monitoring of composite structures through electrical methods.

An innovative approach that integrates synergically these two frameworks was proposed as a powerful tool for increasing the reliability, safety and cost-effectiveness of composite structures.

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